

Dot's Home

Developed by: Rise-Home Stories

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Keywords

African American Studies, Ethical Decision-making, Family Dynamics, Gentrification, Housing Justice, Intergenerational Inequality, Poverty, Racial Injustice, Redlining, U.S. History

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Dot's Home* (Rise-Home Stories). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Dot's Home (see Figure 1) is a short activist game released in 2021 by the nonprofit organization Rise-Home Stories to raise awareness about housing discrimination, gentrification, and land justice within Black communities in the USA. Learners play as Dot, a young Black woman living in a Detroit neighborhood with her nephew and grandmother. The player time-travels to three past scenes to learn about the housing challenges faced by Dot's community in each of these historic periods. At the end of the time-travel sequences, the player helps Dot's family make an important decision about their housing. These choices are remembered and lead to different endings. However, most players' choices do not meaningfully impact the game's narrative, since the illusion of choice was an explicit design

feature intended to highlight how some systems are rigged against the individual (Morris, 2022).

Facts

Release date:	October 22, 2021
Developer:	Rise-Home Stories
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	60–90 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	Smartphones, tablets, Mac computers, or Windows PCs.
Material:	There is optional material on Rise-Home Stories' website that provides context to the story of Dot's Home.
Price:	Available for free

Resonance & Criticism

The game was well received by critics and players alike. Dot's Home was positively reviewed in an IGN article in 2021 and a Wired article in 2022 (Morris, 2022; Valentine, 2021). Players have also rated the game well; in 2025, Dot's Home has a "Very Positive" rating on Steam, 4.4/5 stars on the Google Play Store with over 10,000 downloads, and 4.5/5 stars on the App Store.

The game received mixed reviews from Shelterforce, a nonprofit publication that reports on affordable housing (Duong, 2022). The reviewer criticized the quality of the dialogue, the illusion of choice, and felt that important nuance was lost due to the game's short length. However, Shelterforce praised the game for its art direction and the immersive qualities of its game design (Duong, 2022).

Game Principle & Process

Dot's Home is a short point-and-click narrative experience in which the player explores the environment, inspects objects, and converses with other characters. The game is divided into three main chapters, with an introduction and an epilogue. Each chapter begins with Dot time-traveling to the past, where she meets her ancestors and speaks with them. In these dialogues, the player is provided with multiple dialogue options and conversational threads. Through these conversations, the player learns about the housing issues and discrimination impacting the lives of Dot's ancestors. The player can optionally find and read newspaper clippings throughout the environment that provide additional historical context for each era.

While the story is linear, at the end of each time-travel sequence, the player advises one of Dot's family members on a significant life decision about their home, such as whether to sell

it to an immigrant family or to wealthy out-of-state investors. These choices ask the player to consider how the decisions they make for Dot's family will affect the whole community, an intentional design choice by the developers to create a "values-driven game" (Morris, 2022). Each player's decision is recorded and will lead to one of three possible conversations between Dot and her family at the end of the game. With this one exception, players have limited agency and control over the story's outcome. Restricting the player's power over the game narrative was another intentional design choice to illustrate how prejudicial systems can limit an individual's power and control over their life (Morris, 2022).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The primary goal of Dot's Home is to situate the player in the role of an individual directly impacted by harmful systems that dictate where people of color can live in the United States. The player is inserted into scenarios where they must make housing decisions in a community affected by redlining, urban renewal, and gentrification. The developer's explicit learning goal is to encourage player reflection on how families and communities end up in specific neighborhoods, using the game to emphasize that not everyone has equal choice in determining how and where they live due to factors like race, immigration status, and wealth (Rise-Home Stories Project, 2021).

The game is free and available on all smartphones and computers, so little or no additional equipment is required. Dot's Home can be downloaded through platforms such as Steam or the App Store, or directly from the Rise-Home Stories' website.

Instructors can find a wealth of free additional resources on housing issues on Rise-Home Stories' website. Dot's Home is also part of the Rise-Home Stories Project, a collection of media intended to educate the public about housing discrimination and policy. These additional resources and media stories could be assigned to students alongside Dot's Home to provide context for the topics the game addresses, including current housing issues faced by communities of color in the United States.

Given the short length of Dot's Home and the game's focus on the Detroit community, it is not well-equipped to give students a broad, thorough understanding of the history of housing discrimination. However, Dot's Home strongly positions the game as a powerful supplementary learning tool to communicate the individualized impact and emotional experience of living through racialized housing discrimination. Since the game is single-player, it may be helpful to ask students to reflect on their experiences before, during, and after the game to encourage engagement. Dot's Home would help facilitate a larger class discussion on the impacts of historic housing discrimination, gentrification, and land justice.

Effectiveness

There have been no empirical studies on the effectiveness of Dot's Home as a tool for raising awareness of housing discrimination, land justice, and gentrification. However, the game is

narrative-driven, with simple gameplay more akin to an interactive novel, making it a beginner-friendly and accessible experience for those unfamiliar with digital games. The game has also been praised for its immersive storytelling (Duong, 2022).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Dot's Home explores "the human side of housing injustice instead of giving meticulous explanations about history and policy" (Duong, 2022). Given the narrative focus on the experience of one community within a specific city, if the game is played in isolation, players lacking context for the broader history of discriminatory housing policies may draw simplified conclusions about how these complex issues work. However, Dot's Home provides a concrete example of how real housing laws impact people and communities. The strength of Dot's Home lies in its ability to ground abstract ideas and statistics through storytelling. To succeed as an educational tool, Dot's Home should be situated within a larger historical context and supplemented with learning materials or lectures that comprehensively illustrate the consequences of housing discrimination across different communities, regions, and time periods.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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